

**THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF NEW ADJECTIVES IN THE LEXICON OF
THE UZBEK AND KHRAKALPAK LANGUAGES****Abdullaev Okhunjon.***Teacher of Karakalpak State University.*

Abstract. This article is devoted to the role and importance of new words in the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages. Examples of new borrowed words are given, comments are made about their impact on the vocabulary and recommendations are given.

Key words: *lexeme, borrowed word, term, neologism, dictionary, own layer.*

Many types of dictionaries have been created today. However, they should be perfected and updated in accordance with the spirit of the times. For example, let's take the spelling dictionary of the Uzbek language. Since 1929, more than 20 spelling dictionaries of the Uzbek language have been compiled. But of these, the most complete spelling dictionary covers only 65,000 words and word forms that experts believe will satisfy the student [1; 632] it can be said that it has partially lost its importance today. "Rules of spelling of the Uzbek language" approved on August 24, 1995 by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan made changes to the orthographic standards. Since then, there have been disputes even among experts about the correct spelling of some words. For example, *plot - plot, budget - budget, September - September.*

In order to put an end to this, in order to specify the spelling of all words in our language, in 2013, A. Madvaliyev and E. Begmatov prepared for publication the "Spelling dictionary of the Uzbek language" covering more than 85,000 words that can meet the demand of specialists and the public (-T. , Akademnashr, 2013) is one of the important news of this day.

The new multi-volume explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language is a two-volume dictionary created in 1981 [2; 38] is not a revised edition of the [3; 65]. The interpretation of word forms in the new dictionary is based on the new achievements of lexicography. Examples include:

a) choosing the dominant form of words with the same general lexical meaning, and not giving the rest in cases where there is no change in meaning;

b) a new approach to historical, ethnographic, religious terms given (or not given at all) in the previous dictionary under signs such as "obsolete", "religious";

c) shows the unique features of the new dictionary, such as giving as complete information as possible to words and terms other than the Uzbek and All-Turkish lexicons (belonging to Arabic, Persian, international, Russian, etc. languages).

A dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language and an explanatory dictionary of synonyms have already been created. However, it is not possible to find and observe the synonymy of many words, the stylistic differentiation of synonyms. Also, it is now recognized by all linguists that graduonymic series differs from synonymous series. An uncommented example of this dictionary was created by Sh. Bobojonov and I. Islamov. Accordingly, the creation and expansion of the dictionary of literal synonyms of the Uzbek language, as well as the detailed development of the graded words in the language system in an explanatory manner, are raised as an issue of the agenda. So, it is no exaggeration to say that such problems of philological dictionaries have accumulated since the period of lexicography in the 80s. "An explanatory dictionary of the Karakalpak language" was published in 1992 and consisted of 4 volumes. A new edition of the explanatory dictionary was prepared by the Terminology Center under the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. This work was headed by the head of the terminology center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, professor Sh. Abdinazimov. The new explanatory dictionary, enriched with some new words, raised the development of the Karakalpak language to a new level.

Lexical development goes in two directions. On the one hand, the lexicon is enriched by expressing the historical changes and innovations that occurred in the development of society in the course of its development. The lexicon is enriched by words adopted in other languages, new words created, new terms, new phrases, and changes in their meanings. Changes in the vocabulary do not depend on the language system. On the other hand, the lexicon is enriched due to the creation of new words with the help of existing words.

The above-mentioned process is directly related to the language level (grammar).

The words that have entered the lexicon in a way that is not directly related to the level of the language partially represent a certain period and society in which they were formed.

The development and enrichment of vocabulary is carried out in the following ways:

1. By acquiring words from other languages;
2. Changing the meaning of words:
 - a) complete change of word meaning;
 - b) appearance of homonyms;
 - d) expansion of word meanings;

Languages are not completely separated from each other. A language can absorb sounds, words and concepts from another language.

Acquisition, i.e. further increase of the vocabulary of the language being acquired, is enriched by making the acquired neologisms more perfect, sonorous, i.e. relying on the rules of the acquired language.

Own layer means words belonging to this language and their formations, as well as words made from words of other languages with their additions. It is not always easy to differentiate between native words and assimilated words. When distinguishing between them, work is done taking into account the semantic, morphological, phonetic features of the word.

It is known that in the course of the historical development of linguistics since the 20th century, the comparative study of language phenomena, taking examples in the necessary places, was carried out on the basis of the theory of Russian linguistics. The vocabulary of the present period cannot be limited only to this situation. Today, among industrialized (capitalist) countries, electronic dictionaries and language automation are much more advanced than other countries. As this issue is put on the agenda, it will be necessary to work on the dictionary experiences of the USA, England, Germany, France, and Russia in the field of wordnet and electronic dictionaries.

Another advantage of language automation is that when people feel the need for language events in a certain work process, it is envisaged that they will perform the tasks of a perfect editor, such as spelling, pronunciation, synonyms, and choosing a word from synonyms that matches the stylistic norm. In computer language, there is no need for the user (user) to carry dozens of dictionaries to work in the official language. Many of these programs have already been created in the national languages mentioned above.

After independence, a lot of theoretical and practical work was started on the defined tasks. However, as mentioned above, dictionaries are created through hard work and require many years of time. The new edition of the 5-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" created at the expense of such hard work, and the 12-volume National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, which is being created, are proof of our above opinion.

Linguists believe that the most important feature of any language and vocabulary is that it is in motion and changing. One of the ways to enrich the vocabulary of such a language is through the acquisition of words from other languages.

The process of language acquisition is mainly related to the expansion of international relations, the formation of market relations, the large-scale trade of goods, the need to express

new concepts within the framework of ideological or social relations, the transition of society from a certain system to a new form. As a result of the rapid development of science and technology and the exchange of ideas between people speaking different languages on the basis of the Internet system, after the 90s of the 20th century, the internationalization of words and terms related to globalized modern technologies increased. Also, this situation is related to changes in the political, spiritual, cultural and economic spheres of society.

In the assimilation of new words in this period, first of all, the introduction of words related to the political sphere, such as president, speaker, parliament, increased, and in some cases, their use became more active. Also, new words related to science and technology, such as computer, display, file, monitoring, user, player, pager, words related to economy, such as auditor, barter, dealer, broker, and words related to cultural sphere, hit, hit-parade, and show are among these.

After independence, the position of the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages increased, especially in the socio-political, spiritual life, in the work in state offices and in the press. Special attention has been paid to the effective use of the beautiful possibilities of our language, to show its expressiveness and attractiveness, and to bring in words and phrases that are generalized at the international level in accordance with the laws of our language. It is known from history that the Turkic languages, which have been improved for a long time, have gained their place at the international level.

Large-scale prose and poetic works were created in the Turkish language, which is considered the ancestor of languages such as Uzbek, Kazakh, and Kyrgyz, and royal works such as "Khamsa" of universal importance were created. The Uzbek and Karakalpak languages, which have developed for many centuries, are getting rich due to the borrowed words of many languages and have been giving words to many languages.

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